

FDO Bulletin 2025-1

March 2025

1. FDO Conference to be in Europe and shifted to spring 2026
2. FDO Forum Phase in Action (SC extension process and AC built)
3. New FDOF Website ready for commenting
4. FDO Memo to clarify various open questions
5. FDO Compliance Profiles to evaluate your implementation
6. FDO Operations paper finished
7. FDO Layered Architecture, Security and Active FDOs
8. FDO Summit Proceedings are finally available
9. New Specification Work
10. Workshop Announcements

1. FDO Conference 2026

Given the situation we concluded that an FDO conference in the US is currently not possible for various known reasons. Therefore, we decided to plan the next FDO conference in Europe again and since we need sufficient preparation time, we shifted the date to spring 2026. We are now discussing the key pillars of the program where the topics already discussed will remain: (1) the layered architecture of the global integrated dataspace with FDOs as basic layer, (2) Interoperability challenges at the basic layers, (3) FDO implementations and applications, (4) advancing the International FDO Testbed, (5) new opportunities given by FDO Operations and Active FDOs. Another key topic could be to add a session on the ongoing discussion about reliability, accountability and persistence as key characteristics of the coming data domain.

Comments and suggestions on the conference topics are welcome.

2. FDO Forum Phase II

The FDO Forum finalized its start of the new FDOF II phase by (1) putting the new [lightweight governance](#) into practice, (2) refreshing the SC following the procedures, (3) initializing an Advisory Committee and (4) restarting the Working Groups. All is now documented on the new website to achieve more transparency. To have proper representation of active groups and the international community the following people were nominated and elected according to the new procedures: Stian Soiland-Reyes (UK), Laura Biven (US), Rossella Aversa (IT/DE), Tshiamo Motshegwa (BO/ZA), Erik Schultes (NL/US). We should note that for the next round of SC changes we will organize an open nomination process.

An Advisory Committee has been initiated including many former SC members whose foci changed over the time. FDOF is eager to invite experts from different backgrounds to participate in the AC. Suggestions are very welcome.

GWDG in Germany took over organisational/administrational support from Naturalis whom we would thank for the four years of support. Sonja Sternkopf (GWDG) will help in organizing and managing the FDOF.

FDOF is now back in operational mode after the phase of refreshing its structures.

3. New Website

The FDOF [website](#) was completely refreshed as well and is now hosted by the GWDG. It contains all “old” information which is still relevant such as the FDO Specification documents, but it also contains some new features such as the governance structure and processes, explanatory documents and participation options. The transformation of the “fairdo.org” domain took a bit longer than expected which caused the website to not be accessible for a few days.

We are still in the process of optimizing the content and layout, which is why we welcome all comments to improve it.

FDOF welcomes all suggestions for improving the layout and the content of the new website.

4. FDO Memos

Increasingly often we received questions such as “Is FDO a new metadata standard?”, “Are FDOs secure?”, “What is the difference between FDO and Data Products”, etc. FDOF therefore decided to formulate short statements on some of these aspects meant as clarifications. You can find them here: <https://fairdo.org/fdo-memos/>

FDOF will create memos for clarifying often heard questions. Please, comment and give us further topics where clarifications would be useful.

5. FDO Compliance Profiles/Interoperability

At the FDO Summit in Berlin it was obvious that many presenters were not aware of the FDO specifications and had their own definitions. However, this would hamper interoperability with respect to such a basic issue. Erik Schultes from GOFAIR suggested creating Compliance Profiles that could indicate the degree of compliance and the tasks to be accomplished. We would now like to ask all colleagues who worked on implementing FDOs to fill in a small set of questions. FDOF will ask experts to evaluate the submitted CP and give advice for optimizations. You can find the template to be filled in here:

<https://fairdo.org/fdo-compliance-profiles/>

FDOF would like to ask all FDO implementers to fill in the CP template and to help in harmonizing the usage of FDOs.

6. FDO Operations

Core FDOs are basically “passive” entities bundling useful information about data in a persistent way. However, in many cases users want to associate operations with such FDOs. A TSIG subgroup under the lead of Nicolas Blumenröhr (KIT) now finalized a paper on FDO Operations. It describes different options of associating operations with FDOs and refers to concrete examples. The most general way is to manage an operation registry to specify relations between FDO-Types and operations. There are several ways to do this association which is described in this excellent [paper](#).

A [white paper](#) about “Active FDOs” has been written which are autonomous acting agents exchanging standardized messages. These aFDOs include operations in a restricted way to deal with trust and security concerns. A paper describing aFDOs in more detail is in progress. Their security aspects are comparable to those dealt with in dataspace technology stacks (see point 7).

An FDO Memo on terminology differentiating between Core FDOs, FDO Operations and active FDOs is in progress.

FDOF welcomes experts who would like to participate in the ongoing discussions about aFDOs.

7. FDO Layered Architecture, Security and aFDOs

The interactions with industry about dataspace technology are ongoing and of great importance since also in research not all data are open. For protected data the research domain will have to

apply the same kind of security measurements as industry¹. Already in the last bulletin we presented the layered architecture (see diagram) where we believe the Core FDOs are a basic interoperability layer and where either Dataspace Technology or aFDOs form layers on top to deal with reuse control according to formal policies. This layered system has been implemented in the FDO One project.

Recent discussions have shown that there is a trend in industry towards concepts such as reliability, accountability and persistence. Many are realizing that the current way of doing things is not leading to a stable domain of data where trust can be established. Just take the AI domain where we will see that thousands of small and big models will be traded, where AI models will be tuned to new models, where data producers contribute with their data collections to the training successes etc. A rethinking of strategies seems to be urgent, emphasizing the need for true persistent identifiers and FDOs.

FDOF TSIG has now established a subgroup to work on these layer and security aspects. Every expert in these issues is welcome to participate with the intention of writing a paper and preparing a workshop.

FDO TSIG created a subgroup working on these security aspects which are comparable in dataspace technologies and active FDOs. If you would like to participate, send a short email via this form: <https://fairdo.org/contact-responsibility/> .

8. FDO Summit Proceedings

Finally, after hard work to get all bits and bytes together including the reviews and the paper updates the proceedings of the FDO Summit 2024 have been published. This is a great moment to document progress in the area of FDOs. We would like to thank all authors, reviewers, and particularly the TIB staff, including Claudia Biniossek and Dirk Betz, for getting this all done. You can find the proceedings here: <https://doi.org/10.52825/ocp.v5i>.

9. New FDO Specifications

After consolidating the early [FDO specification documents](#) and a first phase of implementing them in concrete projects, it is now time to review and extend them. The Requirements Specification document should be turned into a much more structured document based on 2 years of experience, additional specifications need to be made for the mandatory kernel attributes and those that are required for [Data FDOs](#). FDOF will also discuss the consequences of FDO Operations and active FDOs with respect to additional specifications.

¹ It should be noted that there is an increasing discussion that global players will use open data without acknowledgement and payments for commercial purposes. It can be that new protection mechanisms will be required even for “open data” to prevent commercial misuse.

FDOF welcomes experts who would like to participate in these activities which will be taken up by the FDO TSIG WG.

10. Announcements/Workshops

The FDOF is working again on a workshop program which will widely focus on practical data infrastructure work and FDO implementations. The following workshops are planned (see [here](#)):

- 7. April: The EPOS research infrastructure: challenges and solutions
- 19. May: The Norwegian Research Data Archive challenges and solutions
- May/June: FDO Operations: concepts, choices and practical implementations
- ??: workshop on security issues in the layered architecture and aFDOs

FDOF welcomes suggestions for further open workshops that are related to the core ideas behind FAIR Digital Objects. For suggestions, please, go here: <https://fairdo.org/contact-responsibility/>.

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For Comments/questions go here: <https://fairdo.org/contact-responsibility/>**